

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for NRF2 (Q16236) for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation and flow cytometry

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Abstract

NRF2 (Nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2) is a master transcription factor that regulates cellular redox homeostasis and cytoprotective responses. Here we have characterized seventeen NRF2 commercial antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and flow cytometry using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While the use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

UniProt ID Q16236, *NFE2L2*, NRF2, Nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

NRF2, encoded by the *NFE2L2* gene, is a key transcription factor that regulates cellular antioxidant and cytoprotective responses (1). Under normal conditions, it is inhibited by KEAP1, but oxidative stress triggers its activation and nuclear translocation, where it induces antioxidant response element (ARE)-dependent genes. While NRF2 activation protects against oxidative damage and inflammation, persistent activation is associated with cancer progression and therapy resistance (2). NRF2 is also implicated in the pathogenesis of Parkinson's disease, and its protective role remains explored (3).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (4). It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available renewable antibodies against the corresponding protein (4). Here, we characterized seventeen commercial NRF2 antibodies, selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturers, in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and flow cytometry. In addition, four additional antibodies were tested in a subset of these assays. The identification of high-quality antibodies provides a foundation for reliable cellular analysis of NRF2 expression, regulation and function.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (5) and in Table 5 of this data note (4).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cells (6, 7). The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million "TPM" + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (8). The HCT 116 expresses the *NFE2L2* transcript at $6.3 \log_2$ TPM+1, and an *NFE2L2* KO HCT 116 cell line was obtained from Abcam (Table 1). Moreover, as seen on DepMap, the HCT 116 does not carry mutations in the *NFE2L2* that could affect antibody–epitope binding.

Under basal conditions, endogenous NRF2 protein levels are kept low through continuous degradation by the proteasome. As a result, detection of endogenous NRF2 typically requires treatment with the proteasome inhibitor MG-132 (9). In Figure 1A, HCT 116 WT and *NFE2L2* KO were treated with $10 \mu\text{M}$ final concentration of MG-132 overnight and compared with the untreated cells. One renewable antibody

was used for the western blot which shows an increase in NRF2 levels in the treated HCT 116 WT cells while this signal is absent in the KO treated cells. To screen nineteen antibodies (Table 2) in western blot, protein lysates from MG-132-treated WT and *NFE2L2* KO were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with the nineteen NRF2 antibodies in parallel (Figure 1B).

We next assessed the ability of nineteen antibodies (Table 2) to capture endogenous from MG-132 treated HCT 116 protein extracts by immunoprecipitation, followed by western blot analysis. Following immunoprecipitation, successful target capture results in depletion of from the unbound (UB) fraction, which represents the lysate remaining after incubation with the antibody-bead conjugate and contains any uncaptured protein. In this assay, the immunoprecipitated (IP) fractions could not be directly analyzed by western blot due to interference from antibody heavy chains co-eluted during the immunoprecipitation step. Therefore, equal amounts of starting material (SM) and the corresponding UB fractions were resolved side by side by SDS-PAGE to assess capture efficiency. A reduction in levels in the UB relative to the SM is indicative of successful immunoprecipitation of the target protein (Figure 2). For the western blotting step, a previously validated NRF2 antibody was used (Figure 1).

For flow cytometry (Figure 3), untreated or MG-132-treated HCT 116 WT and *NFE2L2* KO cells were labelled with distinct fluorescent dyes and combined at a 1:1 ratio. Both cell lines were fixed, permeabilized and blocked in the same tube prior to antibody staining to reduce bias. Nineteen antibodies (Table 3) were then evaluated, with fluorescent intensity assessed using the Attune NxT flow cytometer. Antibody staining in both WT and KO line was then quantified using FlowJo software, with representative histograms presented in Figure 3.

In conclusion, we have screened nineteen NRF2 commercial antibodies in western blot and immunoprecipitation, and nineteen by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human HCT 116 WT and *NFE2L2* KO cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 5 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all three applications (8). High-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect NRF2 were identified in all applications. Researchers who wish to study NRF2 in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available NRF2 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners. We encourage readers to consult vendor documentation to identify the specific antigen each antibody is raised against, where such information is available.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in NRF2, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. NRF2 experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) (4). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

The cell lines are listed in Table 1. Primary antibodies used in western blot and immunoprecipitation are listed in Table 2. Primary antibodies used in flow cytometry are in Table 3, and all secondary antibodies are listed in Table 5. To ensure consistency with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations (where antibody concentrations are not disclosed), antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios rather than absolute concentrations. To facilitate proper citation and unambiguous identification, all cell lines and antibodies are referenced with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) (10, 11). All cell lines used in this study were regularly tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

For MG-132 treatment, 10 μ M final concentration of MG-132 (Cell Signaling Technology, cat. number 2194) was added to HCT 116 cells and kept overnight (~18 h).

Antibody screening by western blot

Untreated or MG-132-treated HCT 116 WT and *NFE2L2* KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000 \times g for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated with the membranes in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) or Clarity Western ECL Substrate

(Bio-Rad, cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). All tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

MG-132-treated HCT 116 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 x g for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 1 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels.

Antibody screening by flow cytometry

Untreated or MG-132-treated HCT 116 WT and *NFE2L2* KO cells were detached, and nine million cells were labelled with CellTracker green or violet fluorescent dyes, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, #C7025 and #C10094). WT and KO cells were then centrifuged at 300 x g, for 10 minutes and resuspended in PBS containing 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA) (Sigma-Aldrich, A9647). Cell populations were then combined at a 1:1 ratio, centrifuged and fixed on ice for 20 minutes using 800 µL of 4% PFA in PBS (Thermo Fisher Scientific #J19943.K2). Following fixation, 1.2 mL of 1% BSA in PBS was added to the tube, vortexed and centrifuged at 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C. Cells were then permeabilized in 400 µL PBS with 0.1% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific #J19943.K2) for 10 minutes at room temperature, centrifuged at 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C and then blocked with 5% goat serum (Sigma-Aldrich #G6767), 1% BSA in PBS for 30 minutes on ice. After the blocking step 400,000 cells were aliquoted into individually labelled tubes, centrifuged at 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C and incubated in 150µL of 1% BSA PBS with primary NRF2 antibodies for 30 minutes on ice. 500µL of 1% BSA, PBS was then added to each tube, vortexed and centrifuged at 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C. Cells were then incubated with their corresponding Multi-rAb CoraLite Plus 647 secondary antibodies in 150 µl of 1% BSA PBS for 30 minutes on ice. 500 µl of 1% BSA PBS was then added to each tube, vortexed and centrifuged 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C.

Tubes were then resuspended in 1 ml of 1% BSA in PBS and data was acquired using the Attune NxT flow cytometer. Data was analysed using FlowJo with the following gates. The cell population was first gated on FSC-A vs SSC-A, within that gate single cells were selected by FSC-A vs FSC-H and then KO and WT cells were isolated by BL1-A vs VL1-A using a quadrat gate. Quantification of antibody staining was then observed in the RL1-A channel and histograms merged to demonstrate the staining intensity between the

two populations compared to the two secondary only controls. The figure was then assembled using Adobe Illustrator 2025.

Data availability

Underlying data

Zenodo: Dataset for the NRF2 antibody screening study <DOI>

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Synaptic Systems, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Abcam	ab288559	CVCL_0291	HCT 116	WT
Abcam	ab287647	CVCL_B8LH	HCT 116	<i>NFE2L2</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the NRF2 antibodies tested in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
abcam	ab62352**	1062169-44	AB_944418	recombinant mono	EP1808Y	rabbit	0.73	Wb, FC, IF
ABclonal	A21176**	3522122857	AB_3661892	recombinant mono	ARC50393	rabbit	0.93	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP38744_P050	QC8434	AB_3698280	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP38745_T100	QC8435-20060810	AB_841576	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP2-67465**	HO1224	AB_3353597	recombinant mono	SU0334	rabbit	1.00	Wb
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP3-21580**	250314	AB_3622288	recombinant mono	SR2277	rabbit	0.00	Wb, IP, IF
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	MAB3925*	CAIQ0124091	AB_2263162	monoclonal	383727	mouse	0.50	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	20733**	3	AB_2934224	recombinant mono	E5F1A	rabbit	0.20	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	33649**	1	AB_2922991	recombinant mono	E3J1V	rabbit	0.10	Wb, IP
Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank (DSHB)	PCRPNFE2L2-1D12*	7/11/19	AB_2618882	monoclonal	PCRPNFE2L2-1D12	mouse	0.02	IP
Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank (DSHB)	PCRPNFE2L2-3D2*	7/11/19	AB_2618883	monoclonal	PCRPNFE2L2-3D2	mouse	0.04	IP
GeneTex	GTX103322	45616	AB_1950993	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.26	Wb, FC, IP, IF
GeneTex	GTX135165	43965	AB_2887459	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.63	Wb
GeneTex	GTX635826**	45271	AB_2909905	recombinant mono	HL1021	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
GeneTex	GTX640822**	45551	AB_3698345	recombinant mono	HL3183	rabbit	1.00	Wb
MilliporeSigma	ZRB1493**	Q3476104	AB_3739852	recombinant mono	5B20	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Proteintech	16396-1-AP	00145459	AB_2782956	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.90	Wb, IF
Proteintech	80593-1-RR**	23019843	AB_2918904	recombinant mono	1I21	rabbit	1.00	Wb, FC, IP, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-38583*	AC4649938	AB_2898495	monoclonal	1A6G6	mouse	1.00	Wb

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody, NA=not available

Table 3: Summary of the NRF2 antibodies tested in flow cytometry

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab62352**	1062169-66	AB_944418	recombinant mono	EP1808Y	rabbit	0.73	Wb, FC, IF
Abclonal	A21176**	6100010967	AB_3661892	recombinant mono	ARC50393	rabbit	1.10	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP38744_P050	QC8434	AB_3698280	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP38745_T100	QC8435-20060810	AB_841576	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	MAB3925*	CAIQ0124091	AB_2263162	monoclonal	383727	mouse	0.50	Wb
Cell Signalling Technology	12721**	10	AB_2715528	recombinant mono	D1Z9C	rabbit	1.11	Wb, FC, IF, IP
Cell Signalling Technology	20733**	3	AB_2934224	recombinant mono	E5F1A	rabbit	0.20	Wb
Cell Signalling Technology	33649**	1	AB_2922991	recombinant mono	E3J1V	rabbit	0.10	Wb, IP
DSHB	PCRP-NFE2L2-1D12*	7/11/19	AB_2618882	monoclonal	PCRP-NFE2L2-1D12	mouse	0.02	IP
DSHB	PCRP-NFE2L2-3D2*	7/11/19	AB_2618883	monoclonal	PCRP-NFE2L2-3D2	mouse	0.04	IP
Genetex	GTX103322	45616	AB_1950993	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.26	Wb, FC, IP, IF
Genetex	GTX135165	43965	AB_2887459	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.63	Wb
Genetex	GTX635826**	45824	AB_2909905	recombinant mono	HL1021	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Genetex	GTX640822**	45551	AB_3698345	recombinant mono	HL3183	rabbit	1.00	Wb
MilliporeSigma	ZRB1493**	Q3447389	AB_3739852	recombinant mono	5B20	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Proteintech	16396-1-AP	00176666	AB_2782956	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.90	Wb, IF
Proteintech	80593-1-RR**	23019843	AB_2918904	recombinant mono	1121	rabbit	1.00	Wb, FC, IP, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	710574**	2491620	AB_2532742	recombinant poly	21HCLC	rabbit	0.50	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-38583*	79541092	AB_2898495	monoclonal	1A6G6	mouse	1.00	Wb

Wb=western blot; FC=Flow cytometry; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody

Table 4: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration (µg/µL)	Working concentration (µg/mL)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.05
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM001	AB_3068333	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.5
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 555-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR003	AB_3073507	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.5
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 555-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM003	AB_3068539	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.5
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 647-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR005	AB_3073509	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.83
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 647-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM005	AB_3073503	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.83

Table 5: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence and flow cytometry

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Figure 1: NRF2 antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: NRF2 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 3: NRF2 antibody screening by flow cytometry (part 1)

Figure 3: NRF2 antibody screening by flow cytometry (part 2)

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: NRF2 antibody screening by western blot.

A) Lysates of HCT 116 WT and *NFE2L2* KO untreated or treated with 10 μ M MG-132 overnight were prepared, and 30 μ g of protein were processed for western blot with anti-NRF2 33649** at 1/1000. **B)** MG-132-treated HCT 116 WT and *NFE2L2* KO were processed for western blot with the indicated NRF2 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab62352** at 1/1000, A21176** at 1/1000, ARP38744_P050 at 1/500, ARP38745_T100 at 1/1000, NBP2-67465** at 1/1000, NBP3-21580** at 1/1000, MAB3925* at 1/500, 20733** at 1/1000, 33649** at 1/1000, PCRP-NFE2L2-1D12* at 1/50, PCRP-NFE2L2-3D2* at 1/100, GTX103322 at 1/500, GTX135165 at 1/1000, GTX635826** at 1/1000, GTX640822** at 1/1000, ZRB1493** at 1/1000, 16396-1-AP at 1/2000, 80593-1-RR** at 1/1000, MA5-38583* at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 67.8 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: NRF2 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

MG-132-treated HCT 116 WT lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed for 1 h using 0.5 mg of lysate and 2.0 μ g of the indicated NRF2 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. UB samples were collected and run side-by-side with the SM then processed for western blot with the NRF2 antibody GTX640822** used at 1/200. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=6% starting material; UB=6% unbound fraction. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 3: NRF2 antibody screening by flow cytometry.

HCT 116 WT and *NFE2L2* KO cells untreated or treated with 10 μ M MG-132 overnight were labelled with a green or violet, fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed in a 1:1 ratio, fixed in 4% PFA and permeabilized in 0.1% Triton X-100. 400,000 cells were stained with the indicated NRF2 antibodies and corresponding Multi-rAb CoraLite® Plus 647 secondary antibodies. Antibody staining was quantified using the Attune NxT Flow Cytometer with representative images showing the staining intensity in the KO population (pink histogram, dashed line) compared to the WT cells (green histogram, solid line). Histograms with dotted lines represent secondary antibody-only controls in both WT and KO cells. Antibody dilutions used: ab62352** at 1/7270, A21176** at 1/11000, ARP38744_P050 at 1/5000, ARP38745_T100 at 1/5000, MAB3925* at 1/5000, 12721** at 1/11000, 20733** at 1/2000, 33649** at 1/1000, PCRP-NFE2L2-1D12* at 1/350, PCRP-NFE2L2-3D2* at 1/710, GTX103322 at 1/2600, GTX135165 at 1/16300, GTX635826** at 1/10000, GTX640822** at 1/10000, ZRB1493** at 1/1000, 16396-1-AP at 1/9000, 80593-1-RR** at 1/10000, 710574** at 1/5000, MA5-38583* at 1/1000. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.